

Reported user-generated online hate speech: The ‘ecosystem’, frames, and ideologies

Iztok Šori ¹ and Vasja Vehovar ^{2*}

¹ Peace Institute, Metelkova ulica 6, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia; iztok.sori@mirovni-institut.si; Tel.: +3861234 7720

² University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Social Sciences, Kardeljeva ploščad 5, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia; Vasja.Vehovar@fdv.uni-lj.si

* Correspondence: iztok.sori@mirovni-institut.si

Extended legend to the data

Variable group	Variable	Explanation	Type of answer
PRE-CODING			
	Nr. of the report	Number of the report in the database of the monitoring organization.	[Number]
	Date of the report	Date when the statement was reported to the monitoring organization.	[Date]
	Reported URL	URL where the statement was published.	[URL]
	Reported content	Content of the report.	[Text]
	Category	Category of the statement as defined by the monitoring organisation.	Intolerant speech against a specially protected group or a member of that group, without any element of intent (Nestrpen govor zoper posebej varovano skupino ali pripadnika te skupine, brez elementa naklepa) OR Alleged unlawful hate speech (Domnevno nezakonit sovražni govor)
	Comment of the person who reported	Comment submitted to the monitoring organization by the person who reported.	[Text]
GENERAL			
	Date of coding	Date when the researcher performed the coding.	[Date]
	Coded by	Name and surname of the coder.	[Initials]
	Where was the statement published?	Type of media where the statement was published.	News portal (NP) OR Social network (SN) OR forum (F)
	Title of the article if applicable	The title of the article to which the user statement refers.	[Text]
TARGET GROUPS			

	Migrants (Y/N)	Does the statement target migrants?	Yes OR No
	Migrants (content)	Specify the target(s).	[Text]
	Religion (Y/N)	Does the statement target religion?	Yes OR No
	Religion (content)	Specify the religious target.	[Text]
	Nationality (Y/N)	Does the statement target nationality?	Yes OR No
	Nationality (content)	Specify the nationality target.	[Text]
	Political (Y/N)	Does the statement target political orientation?	Yes OR No
	Political (content)	Specify the political target.	[Text]
	Sexual orientation (Y/N)	Does the statement target sexual orientation?	Yes OR No
	Sexual orientation (content)	Specify the sexual orientation target.	[Text]
	"Race" (Y/N)	Does the statement target "race"?	Yes OR No
	"Race" (content)	Specify the "race" target.	[Text]
	Gender (Y/N)	Does the statement target gender?	Yes OR No
	Gender (content)	Specify the gender target.	[Text]
	Multiple targets (Y/N)	Does the statement target multiple personal circumstances?	Yes OR No
	METAPHORS		
	Metaphors (all content)	All metaphors used in the statement.	[Text]
	Metaphors present (Y/N)	Are metaphors present in the statement?	Yes OR No
	Pests (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as pests?	Yes OR No
	Pests (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to pests.	[Text]
	Uncivilized (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as uncivilized?	Yes OR No
	Uncivilized (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to uncivilized behaviour.	[Text]
	Violent and criminal (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as violent and criminal?	Yes OR No

	Violent and criminal (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to violence and criminality.	[Text]
	Dirty (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as dirty?	Yes OR No
	Dirty (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to dirt.	[Text]
	Ethnic (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as ethnically different?	Yes OR No
	Ethnic (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to ethnicity.	[Text]
	General (Y/N)	Do the metaphors refer to more general insults?	Yes OR No
	General (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to general insults.	[Text]
	Religious (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as religiously different?	Yes OR No
	Religious (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to religion.	[Text]
	Animal (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as animals?	Yes OR No
	Animal (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to animals.	[Text]
	Disease (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as a disease?	Yes OR No
	Disease (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to disease.	[Text]
	Intellectually inferior (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as intellectually inferior?	Yes OR No
	Intellectually inferior (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to intellectual inferiority.	[Text]
	Sexually deviant (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as sexually deviant?	Yes OR No
	Sexually deviant (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to sexual deviation.	[Text]
	Lazy (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as lazy?	Yes OR No
	Lazy (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to laziness.	[Text]
	Not man enough (Y/N)	Do the metaphors describe migrants as not man enough?	Yes OR No
	Not man enough (content)	Specify the metaphors referring to masculinity.	[Text]
REFERENCES			

	References (all content)	All references used in the statement.	[Text]
	Reference present (Y/N)	Are references present in the statement?	Yes OR No
	Ideology (Y/N)	Do references refer to ideology?	Yes OR No
	Ideology (content)	Specify the references referring to ideology.	[Text]
	Values (Y/N)	Do references refer to values?	Yes OR No
	Values (content)	Specify references referring to values.	[Text]
	Weapons (Y/N)	Do references refer to weapons?	Yes OR No
	Weapons (content)	Specify the references referring to weapons.	[Text]
	Political actors (Y/N)	Do references refer to political actors?	Yes OR No
	Political actors (content)	Specify the references to political actors.	[Text]
	Other (Y/N)	Are other kind of references present in the statement?	Yes OR No
	Other (content)	Specify other references.	[Text]
FRAMING			
	What is the problem?	What does the author describe as problem?	[Text] OR 0 when the diagnosis is not present.
	Who is affected by the problem?	Whom does the author define as passive actor?	[Text] OR 0 when the passive actor is not present.
	FRAME DIAGNOSIS	Define the diagnosis frame.	[Text] OR 0 when the diagnosis is not present.
	What is the solution?	What does the author describe as solution?	[Text] OR 0 when the prognosis is not present.
	Who should provide the solution?	Whom does the author define as active actor?	[Text] OR 0 when the active actor is not present.
	FRAME PROGNOSIS	Define the prognosis frame.	[Text] or 0 when the prognosis is not present.
	Content still available? (Y/N)	Is content still available online?	Yes OR No